

THE RELATIONSHIP OF INSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS IN ORGANIZATIONS AND LIFE CYCLE

Dr. Nejdet Ümit BAŞDAŞ

Orcid: 0000-0002-9755-0134

To cite this article: Dr. Nejdet Ümit Başdaş Current Science, Volume 5, No. 3-5, 2023, p. 01 – 36. - 0099-0001-2303-0201.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

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This article is by Dr. Nejdet Ümit Başdas, Assoc. Prof. Volkan Öngel's doctoral dissertation titled "ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURALIZATION AND THE FORMATION OF INSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS IN SMALL AND MEDIUM SIZED ENTERPRISES AND THE LIFE-CYCLE RELATIONSHIP" dated 3.3.2020, which is a very long study, has been created by taking the data and results of only the institutionalization part without disturbing the semantic integrity of the work. Istanbul, 2023.

ABSTRACT

FORMATION OF INSTITUTIONAL DIMENSIONS AND LIFE CYCLE RELATIONSHIP IN ORGANIZATIONS

Institutional theory (IT) has had relatively little influence on managers and practitioners outside academia. In part, this may be explained by the diminished role of management in determining organizational survival. The assumption that managers have no significant role within IT, however, is not accurate. The very qualitative research is offering an application on a measurement model of the institutional dimensions in organizations and the relation between life cycles and formation of institutional dimensions in SMEs has been searched to analyze the effect of institutionalization process on the development of small and medium- sized enterprises.

Ironically, the institutional approach has yet to become institutionalized. There is little consensus on the measures or methods within this theoretic tradition. This research aimed to introduce a measurement model for institutional dimensions of the organizations and studied the relationship between formation of institutional dimensions and organizations' life-cycles. The research was conducted in 20 small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) and a qualitative approach used.

The originality of the work is the method developed for comparing/measuring the institutional dimension.

Keyword : SME, Small Enterprises, Life cycle, Institutionalisation, Institutional dimensions.

INTRODUCTION

3.42 million SMEs are present in Türkiye as of 2021. (KOSGEB, 2021). This figure equates to 99.8% of all businesses in the nation. Less than 4% of all businesses are classified as small, which are those with less than 10 workers, and medium-sized, which are those with more than 50 employees. The remaining businesses are classified as micro-scale since they employ less than 10 people. As shown in Table 1 below, SMEs are defined as economic entities or firms with annual net sales revenues or financial balance sheets of less than 250 million Turkish Liras and fewer than 250 individuals employed annually. The definition of a SME had its most recent change in 2022. Parallel to this adjustment, SMEs were categorized in the manner described below (CBK 2022).

Table 1. SME Criteria in Türkiye

Definition Criteria	Micro Business	Small Business	Medium Business
Annual Number of Employees	<10	10 – 49	50 – 249
Annual Net Sales (million TL)	≤5	≤50	≤250
Annual Balance Sheet Value (m TL)	≤5	≤50	≤250

Resource: Presidential Decision 2022 / 5315

According to the concept of unity in the 27-country EU, small and medium-sized firms with less than 250 workers make up 99% of all businesses. In the USA, the percentage of small-medium enterprises is 99.9%. The EU SME standards are shown in Table 2:

Table 2. EU SME Criteria

Company category	Number of employees per year	Annual net sales revenue	/ balance sheet total
Medium	< 250	≤ € 50 m	≤ € 43 m
Small	< 50	≤ € 10 m	≤ € 10 m
Micro	< 10	≤ € 2m	≤ € 2m

Resource: “The New SME Definition – User guide and model declaration”-1.1.2015

SMEs are acknowledged as the global driver of economic development. SME production is crucial, but they also contribute to the growth of economic and social democracy. An economic system based on several dynamic SMEs benefits people and their social and family support systems by fostering reciprocal networks among

enterprises, within firms, and among other institutional players, as stated in a 2008 research by Parilli, Bianchi, and Sugden. The stability and short lifespan of these small and medium-sized businesses have become a widespread issue due to the advancements in economics, sociology, and organizational history, and several studies and investigations have been conducted on them from a viewpoint other than business management. It could include an institutional theoretical approach which is difficult to conceptualize outside of management theory. In their article "Crisis in an Evolving Organization," Lippitt and Schimdt recommend that businesspeople learn about the scope and characteristics of various financial crisis states in an organization because these problems are well-known, rigid, and have finite states; however, they also note that it is more challenging to comprehend non-financial problems/crises because they are frequently subjective and have no finite state (Lippitt and Schmidt 1967, 102-112). Several studies have looked at how the institutions around us affect businesses and financial success. After the globalization of markets, SMEs have discovered several chances by collaborating with significant businesses. They cannot be expected to sustain their competitiveness if they disregard these chances, narrow their attention to a single aspect of their duties (such as production or service exclusively), and work in isolation from their surroundings (Singh, Garg, and Deshmukh 2008, 118-121)

Following a comprehensive literature search on SMEs concerned with all such issues as the institution, institutionalization process, organizational life span, life cycle, institutional environment, competitiveness, and institutionalization process indicators/dimensions of SMEs within the disciplines of business administration, management, and sociology. The following impressive finding was obtained after a thorough literature search. Even though there were roughly 45,500 books, articles, and e-books between 1994 and 2018 with the words "SME" or "small and medium-sized enterprises" in the title (1994-2000: 20,000, 2001-2011: 11,500, and 2011-2018: 14,000), there were only six works during that time that mentioned both terms simultaneously. The three publications featuring the term "institutionalization of SMEs" in the title use it wrongly, whereas the other three focus on the institutionalization of a particular discipline within SMEs, such as social

responsibility, e-commerce, and human resources. The topic scanning leads to the conclusion: While there are several research on SMEs in the literature, there are hardly any that specifically address the institutionalization processes in SMEs.

172 items were found after doing a library search using the phrases "institutionalization" and "organization" together in the title of the publication. This is still a relatively small number. The institutional aspect of a field like accounting and human resources in companies has also been covered here. Since the research does not begin with a single or a collection of hypotheses, it will be difficult to identify the beginning point of an academic study in this topic. An inductive method was used as the foundation for the process, which started with a thorough literature review, was followed by topic narrowing and problem-statement determination. Thus, the qualitative research approach was used. The study was conducted on a group of 20 businesses chosen by purposive sampling in four cities of Türkiye. The criteria of organizations with interested managers or partners, from whom the finest information about the study topic can be gathered, as well as the fact that these companies are diverse SMEs, have been taken into consideration as the goal. The analyses of 20 firms were thorough, positivist, interpretive, phenomenological, and descriptive in addition to being in-depth and complete.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Institution and institutionalization process

The notion of institutionalization was born and grown within the field of sociology. A social connections system or group that is established in a society, has its own traditions, legends, and processes, and is constrained by laws is referred to as an institution. The definition of "institution" in the English Collins dictionary is "a large and important institution, such as a long-established university or a long-established bank, or (marriage institution, family) a tradition, procedure, ritual or system that has existed for many years within a certain community or group." Institutions are envisioned as multifaceted/complicated, repeating, self-driven, and productive social processes made up of symbolic components and influenced by a variety of cultural and historical variables (Clegg and Bailey 2008, 684). Philip Selznick contends that institutions are created when certain symbolic features acquire legitimacy, such as societal approval and respectability. Selznick defined institutionalization as adding value above and beyond technical needs. On the other hand, other academics discuss the aspect of social facts / truths that are accepted without contesting the veracity of the idea of institution (Boons and Strannegard 2000, 8). In the institutionalization process, the organization adopts the behaviors and structures that are present in the institutional context in which it is positioned without questioning their validity.

The history of organizational studies within the field of sociology is not very long. American sociologists did not see organizations as distinct social entities that deserved to be studied in their own category until the work of Robert Merton and his students in the late 1940s (Tolbert and Zucker 1996, 175-190). In society, an institution is not merely any organization or organization, to touch on the distinction between institutions and organizations. A collection of individuals coming together for a similar goal under a shared identity is what makes up an organization. 1997's Hirsch and Lounsbury research focuses on how humans play a part in the creation of institutions.

Anthologically in a wide sense institutions are comprised of regulatory, normative, and cultural-cognitive elements that, together with associated activities and resources, provide stability and meaning to social life (Table 3). Regulatory, normative, and cognitive factors often directly influence how a corporation behaves (e.g., internationalization).

Table 3. Three Pillars of Institutions

	Regulator	normative	Cultural – Cognitive
Basis of order	Regulative rules	Binding expectations	Constitutive schema
Basis of compliance	Expedience	Social obligation	Taken-for-grantedness, Shared understandig
Mechanisms	Coercive	Normative	Mimetic
Indicators	Laws, rules, sanctions	Certification Accreditation	Common beliefs, Isomorphism, shared logics of action
Basis of legitimacy	Legally sanctioned	Morally governed	Comprehensive, Recognizabel, Culturally supported
Affect	Fear Guilt / Innocence	Shame / Honor	Certainty / Confusion

Resource: Scott, W. Richard (2014, 60). *Institutions and organizations; ideas, interests, and identities*. California: Sage Publications, Inc.

Legitimacy is an important concept in IT in terms of the survival of institutions. Organizations need more than material resources and know-how to survive and thrive in their social environment. They also need social acceptance and credibility, in short, legitimacy (Scott, Ruef, Mendel & Caronna 2000, 237). To define this important concept: it can be said that it is the general perception of an enterprise's actions being appropriate, correct, acceptable and admirable within a socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs, and definitions.

Institutional Theory

IT is becoming one of the dominant theoretical perspectives in organization theory. Social theory (Hughes 1936; Parson 1951; Selznick 1949) served as the foundation for institutional theory (DiMaggio and Powell 1983, 1991; Meyer and Rowan 1977; Meyer and Scott 1983; Zucker 1987), which is related to the development of assumptions, beliefs, and values underlying organizational characteristics and practices that appear to occur spontaneously (Lemke et al. 2001). According to the theory's understanding, management and organizational practices are the results of social penalties rather than economic consequences.

Through the formal and informal mechanisms, they build, organizations attempt to adjust their structural characteristics to environmental (institutional) circumstances to survive. As can be seen, organizations' longevity relies on environmental harmony. In the time that we might refer to as the "old institutional theory," while the emphasis was on the analysis of processes at the level of individual organizations, the "new institutionalization" concentrated on the interactions between organizational clusters to draw a comparison. The level of analysis was broadened to include many organizational domains. Several degrees of analysis may be found at the organizational level and organizational field levels.

The link and interchange between the organizational field and the company develop and transform institutions, according to the new institutionalization or neo-institutional theory. The new institutional theory acknowledges the interdependence of organizations and their environment. In other words, institutionalization in this circumstance cannot be solely based on the firm's internal operations or the industry in which it operates. The two components exhibit reciprocal reactions to one another and are entangled (Gray 2008).

The institutional environment is now the focus of neo-institutional theory rather than the technological environment. The technological environment, as described by Scott and Meyer (Scott 1987, 512), is the marketplace where goods and services are traded, and where businesses are rewarded for exercising effective and

efficient management over their operational procedures. The idea of institutionalization is not a single, discrete process, according to neo-institutional theory, but rather a collection of processes that alter organizational structures via isomorphism to conform to the preexisting institutional order. The institutional contexts of companies must be strategically managed, which requires an understanding of isomorphism. In the area of organizational studies, DiMaggio, and Powell (1983, 147–160) expanded on the idea of institutional isomorphism theory. "What makes organizations similar?" is one of their great articles. Isomorphism is the theory that best explains this homogeneity. Institutional and competitive dimensions of isomorphism exist. Companies fight not just for resources and clients but also for institutional legitimacy and political clout (DiMaggio and Powell 1977, 159). Imitating one another helps businesses become more legitimate.

Meyer and Rowan's 1977 paper represents a major departure from the conventional structure in terms of the formal structure and the nature of organizational decision-making from which this structure is derived, claim Tolbert and Zucker (1999, 69–184). As a result, in terms of what determines formal structure, emphasis is shifted away from internal production processes, scale, and technology and toward external variables like the establishment of law and the growth of firm social norms. To clarify, it should be noted that the adaptation of these structural rules described includes formal employment policies, social rights, accounting, finance, budget applications/programs, and finance.

Another significant finding from the examination of the last quarter of the 20th century is that formal structures—rather than business or company performance—are more vital for an organization's survival because of its symbolic elements and abstract dimensions. In other words, organizations inside their own institutional context are analogous to these ecosystems because they have access to resources and can live by doing so, based on variables other than the coordination and management of production operations (isomorphic).

To shield their formal structures from the uncertainties of technical and production operations, they must exhibit structural duality (decoupling) between their formal structures and their everyday activities.

This new source of formal structure has rationalized myths as their constituent parts. They are indications of strict institutional regulations that serve as These myths are considered as true because they are extremely institutionalized and impersonal. Workplaces, programs, and technology are some examples. Like how falsehoods are institutionalized and bound in organizations, technologies are. The process of structuring or institutionalizing (formal) structures is the first tenet of neo-institutional theory. Over time, formal structural elements (such as formal function, professional programs, offices, and positions related to personnel rights) are accepted as facts of well-managed organizations. which is.

Life-span and Life Cycles in SMEs

According to studies conducted in the USA on newly established family businesses with a very high percentage of SMEs (US Census Bureau, Family Business Statistics, 2017); 40% of these companies go bankrupt or change hands in the first 5 years, and 66% of the rest in the first generation. The ratio of family businesses that survive until the second generation does not exceed 20%, and only 17% of this 20% can be transferred to the third generation. As a result, only 3.4% of 100 family businesses established in the first generation are transferred to the third generation. The situation in the UK is like the EU D, with a rate of 3.3% (fsb.org.uk 2018).

There are many multiphase organizational life-cycle models. Most models consist of 3 to 10 phases and express a similar organizational development. The four main organizational lifecycle stages are establishment, growth, maturity, and decline. The final stage can turn into revival. In this study, the Life Cycle Model for Small and Medium-Sized Firms (Basdas 2020, 148), which the author analyzed and synthesized dozens of life cycle models and shaped in his fieldwork on SMEs, was used in the thesis that is the basis of this article.

ESTABLISHMENT OF THE RESEARCH MODEL AND METHODOLOGY

There is very little consensus on the definition of key concepts, measures or methods within this theoretic tradition. Unlike population ecology and its Standard measures of density, IT has developed no central use set of standart variables, nor is it associated with a standart research methodology or even a set of methods. (Zucker, 1987, 728). The link between institutionalization processes and life-cycles in small and medium-sized businesses is also little understood.

In-depth interview and observational criteria, as well as the criteria for these criteria, are included in this part along with the research questions. There were three components to the research questions. the institutional characteristics of formal organizations (businesses), the life cycle model of organizations and the stage they are in, and general introduction information about the firm or organization.

A. General descriptive information about the company / organization:
Annex-I Basic Information Sheet

B. Institutional dimensions of formal organizations

The institutional component has been linked to the human aspect, acceptance, learning, adoption, intimidation, and obtaining legitimacy in cultures, as can be observed from the literature review. Institutional measurements are challenging, and there is not even a standard assessment process.

Given the subject's social reality, institutionalization indicators are more indirect than structurization or, for instance, resource reliance, according to Lynne G. Zucker (1987), one of the key players in institutional theory research. He claims that indications may be stated as a result. KT and the institutionalization process have been the subject of several studies,

papers, and observations. The institutional dimension criteria and indicators are summarized here.

1. Presence and adoption of rational myths (Meyer and Rowan, 1977)
 - 1.1. Professional programs (sales, accounting, cost control, ERP, etc.) (Meyer and Rowan 1977)
 - 1.2. Mythified technology(s), technology institutionalized and mythical (Meyer and Rowan 1977)
 - 1.3. Data analysis (observation)
 - 1.4. HR department and formal recruitment policies (competitive isomorphism in addition to Meyer and Rowan: Di Maggio and Powell (1983), job descriptions: Scott (2014))
 - 1.5. HSE programs, practices, and department (Meyer and Rowan, 1977)
 - 1.5.1. “No smoking” sign and other safety signs in and around the building
 - 1.5.2. Smoking areas
 - 1.5.3. Waste recycling bins in offices (observation)
 - 1.6. Social and health insurance opportunities (Meyer and Rowan 1977)
 - 1.7. ISO and practice / degree of adoption (Normative standards, Scott (2014))
 - 1.8. Formalization (Tolbert and Zucker 1999)
 - 1.9. Professionalization (DiMaggio and Powell 1983)+(Zucker 1987)
 - 1.10. Division of labor and specialization (Scott 2014, 96)
 - 1.11. All kinds of certificates, accreditations, approvals (Scott 2014, 60)
 - 1.12. Implementation of an established and written reward system (Meyer and Rowan 1977)
 - 1.13. Presence of management consultant, financial analyst, independent board member or another consultant (Zucker 1987)

2. Institutional dimension observation by results (Zucker 1987)
 - 2.1. Corporate culture
 - 2.1.1. Corporate language, jargon (Meyer and Rowan 1977, 349) + (Zucker 1987)
 - 2.1.2. Established values (Selznick 1957) + (Scott 2014, 96)
 - 2.1.3. Shared beliefs and behaviors (Colbeck 1999)
 - 2.1.4. Shared movement and action logic / Mental models (Calvante 2018)
 - 2.2. Communication and communication channels (Tolbert and Zucker 1999, 179)
 - 2.3. Organizational rigidity, resistance to change, structural duality (Zucker 1987)
 - 2.4. Accepted, generalized business rules (Scott 2014, 96)
 - 2.5. Social activities, participations, projects, donations (Ogava et al. 2002)
3. Institutional dimension observation by cause factors (Institutional study: Lawrence and Suddaby 2013)
 - 3.1. Agents / agents: Leaders, professional organizations, government, government agencies (Scott 1987) + (Fleck 2007)
 - 3.1.1. Developing the learning capabilities of the organization by providing the balance between stability and change because of a leadership practice by institutional actors (leaders) (Fleck 2007) (Ogava et al. 2002)
 - 3.1.2. Management support (Colbeck 1999)
 - 3.2. Judicial relations (Zucker 1987)
 - 3.3. Normative organizations, successful and leading organizations, professional organizations (Zucker 1987)
 - 3.4. International consulting (PWC, Deloitte, etc.) (Zucker 1987)
4. Corporate governance (Melin and Nordqvist 2018) + (Scott 2014, 96)

- 4.1. Family council, family constitution or detailed charter
- 4.2. Succession plan
- 4.3. Independent board member
- 4.4. International partnerships

Finding criteria in this area is difficult. There is no established technique for measuring institutionalism dimensions, even though there is relatively few research on the subject in the literature. Only via close observation and descriptive examination of specific symptoms, traces, causal variables, and outcomes through a qualitative investigation can the abstract institutionalization process—which is difficult to agree on even conceptually—be discovered. In this respect, the interview also employed the recorded responses to the semi-open and open-ended questions in addition to the template in Annex-II, which serves as a reference for the in-depth interviews.

C. The stages in the life-cycle of companies and the life-cycle model
The new Basdas (2020) model, which has three phases and a view, in Annex-III is used. In the used model the first three phases in the model suggested for small and medium-sized businesses are 1. "first," 2. "expansion and integration," and 3. "maturity and structure." The outlook criteria have replaced the fourth stage, which highlights unpredictability in small businesses. Only third tier enterprises are supposed to be judged using the appearance standard. The three states of appearance are active, passive, and decline. The following criteria were used to choose the three states:

- Harmony of business goal and personal goal of partners
- Strategy (Strategy is an important element in determining the structure)
- The degree of development of the organizational structure
- The course of investments
- Management energy level
- The presence of a new leader and the interest of the new generation
- Corporate governance

Method

The main data collecting techniques, in-depth interviews, and observation, as well as sporadically looking at secondary sources, were utilized to gather data for qualitative research. (Creswell 2016, 79, 83.) In-depth interviews and observations were both preferable for taking thorough notes using different note-taking methods.

The basic information sheet was created using secondary data sources, and data was sent to us from the firm to review. Open-ended questions, semi-structured interviewing, and sometimes unstructured interviewing techniques were used to ascertain the traces, indications, causes, and effects associated to the institutionalization dimensions, which make up the second portion and comprise an abstract theme. The life cycle analysis, which makes up the fourth and final element, includes open-ended questions in addition to the structured interview approach.

Sample Size and Scope of Research Companies

A phenomenological research, according to Dukes (1984), recommends working with 3–10 people/subjects. According to John W. Creswell (2016, 158), the sample size will range from 3 to 10 participants. Creswell estimates that 20–30 participants will be used to gather information for the theory in the same book. 20 SMEs were chosen for this study's analysis. The study's scope was maintained broad since a significant sample size is a necessary condition for the validity and reliability of qualitative research.

The sample technique of choice was purposeful sampling. This decision was made in accordance with the qualitative tradition rather than the probability-based quantitative approach (Creswell 2016, 147 and 156). Here, the goal is to identify a purposefully chosen group of individuals or institutions from whom the best data on the study topic may be gathered. Maximum diversity sampling was selected from among the kinds of deliberate sampling for the investigation. So, it was believed that the study would enhance the likelihood that the results would represent various

viewpoints or disparities (Creswell 2016, 157). Criterion-based sampling served as the study's additional sample type. Thus, care was taken to make sure that the participants were individuals who had firsthand knowledge of the phenomena or topic under study. Create a sample of the organizations in the study scope specified in Table 4.

Table 4. SME Status Companies Conducting Qualitative Research

No.	Company	Foundation (year)	Age	Turnover (TL)	Worker (person)
one	Labriz Hotel Tourism Trade LLC	2014	5	1,000,000-	7
2	EDS Injection Molding Inc.	1994	25	110,000,000-	247
3	Mutlu Metal Chemical Industry. Tic.Ltd	1986	33	16,250,000-	11
4	Element Paint Industry and Trade Inc.	2004	15	91,000,000-	87
5	Günak Const.Ind.Trade Inc	1976	43	60,000,000-	140
6	Cheya Hotels & Residences/ Phaselis	2007	12	9,000,000-	38
7	PDR Management Information Consultancy Inc.	1989	30	7,500,000-	40
8	Deteks Chemical Industry Inc.	1966	53	28,000,000-	36
9	Tess Design Consult.Const.LLC	2017	3	650,000-	8
10	Körfezdeniz Const. Trade LLC	2006	13	60,000,000-	175
11	MTM Holography Trust IT Inc	1997	22	22,500,000-	68
12	Oasis Tourism Ltd.	1988	31	14,000,000-	11
13	Adatepe Farm & Food Inc	1998	21	2,000,000-	6+
14	b-fit Health Sports Investment Trade Inc.	2006	13	5,500,000-	21
15	Muzipo Kids Education Consultancy Inc.	2011	8	3,500,000-	12
16	Silk&Cashmere/ Fabeks Foreign Trade Inc.	1992	28	125,000,000-	221
17	e-data Technology LLC	1989	19	103,000,000-	42
18	Varer Machinery Ind.Trade LLC	2006	13	11,000,000-	38
19	Modern Packaging Ind.Trade Inc.	1977	42	40,000,000-	35
20	Saarpor Bosphorus Ind.Trade LLC	2002	17	22,400,000-	48

Different size ranges, being a SME, and not belonging to an international organization are examples of deliberate sampling criteria that assure variety. For this reason, about one third (7 units) of 20 organizations are SMEs with less than \$10

million in annual revenue, roughly another third (7 units) between \$10 and \$50 million in annual revenue, and the remaining one third (6 units) are in the category of SMEs exceeding \$50 million in annual revenue. Requests were sent out on a voluntary basis to over 1400 businesses in Istanbul's four structured industrial zones for this purpose, and 10 businesses were chosen from among 14 returning businesses that were interested to participating in the study and submitting information. To reach the criteria-based diversity ratio, the remaining 10 organizations are chosen within the parameters of the purposive sampling from the researcher's surroundings.

Qualitative Data Analysis

While manual editing or the use of software tools built for qualitative research may be used to construct the data created in the content analysis or qualitative data analysis stage, manual selection was used in this study. It is mentioned by Creswell (2016, 201) and Merriam (2015, 166) that this choice is typical among qualitative researchers, how often it is used, and why. All data were inventoried, and inductive, intuitive, and methodical data analysis procedures such data coding, category development, and axis coding were completed.

Validity and Reliability

For the researcher to watch and evaluate the topic with specific qualifications, Patton (2002, 552) offers the researcher's ethics, experience, and skill as the initial foundation for the validity and reliability of a qualitative study.

One of the validity techniques, the data collecting method, and the confirmation of the collected data were received from the committee composed of three academics and two professional managers within the context of "expert review / assessment" (Merriam 2015, 221). Both the internal and external validity of the research's results were evaluated. The following validation checks were performed.

- a. The need that research results be reliable and significant in and of themselves.
- b. A participant validation strategy was used (Merriam 2015, 207). The validation test was performed at 5 firms that were chosen at random.
- c. To conduct an internal validity test and to ensure consistency in the procedures used for data collection, data interpretation, and measurement in qualitative research, data from all 20 organizations were gathered using pre-made templates and comparable methodologies. Each organization conducted in-depth interviews using the question templates in APPENDIX 1, 2, and 3, followed by workplace observations and lunch, and consistency was assured by analyzing and interpreting the results using same calculation techniques and formulae.
- d. Maximum variety
- e. Theory consistency: The findings and outcomes are mostly in line with theory. According to organizational theory, life cycle models rather than company age or size are used to describe how businesses evolve. The conclusions made in the following results section are in this direction, and the institutional dimension formations are more suited to the organizations' stage of life than they are to their age or size.

The reproducibility of research findings, or "Would the same results emerge if the study is repeated?" is a key indicator of dependability in qualitative research. Detailed descriptions and records of the data collecting processing, analysis, and interpretation processes are also supplied.

FINDINGS, RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

1. In addition to the ideas mentioned in the literature in the context of rational myths, formalization, professionalization, and specialization—the three elements of structuralism—have been added to the institutional dimension / institutionalization indicators, which can be considered as the

institutionalization scale. The research reveals that these ideas have evolved into myths and are mimicked, accepted, and internalized in a similar way as conventional professional practices in occupational safety and health, technology, and programs.

2. The "corporate governance" criteria has been added to the institutional dimension indicators. This criterion has not previously been mentioned in the literature, although it may be one of the causes and have an impact on the organization's future and lifespan.
3. As the literature analysis demonstrates, institutionalization is a rather nebulous/abstract notion, and even academics on the topic are unable to fully agree on its meaning. In addition, there is no established paradigm for quantifying the institutionalization dimension. Several papers have incorporated certain indications, signals, misconceptions (established programs, technologies, etc.), and intermediates as contributing elements in this respect. The "Institutional Dimension Analysis Questions" form in Annex III, which was developed with the addition of the fourth and fifth items because of interviews and observations and created through extensive literature research, can be a measurement tool in this context, or at the very least can be a starting point for additional research.
4. The corporate development and life cycle phases of the firms included in the study, which formed the focus of the research, are measured in Table 5. The following evaluation factors were utilized to determine the institutionalization ratings given here:

In-depth interview notes were gathered in detail, and where it was required, descriptive analysis of the observations was repeated (content analysis is recommended for somewhat more phenomenal or confusing topics). The interview was recorded for each organization, and semi-closed and open questions were used. After the interview, the notes were examined for institutional significance, and any obvious abstract indications, signals, or concrete myths were exposed. The institutional scale is presented in Annex-III. The first component, the existence of

rational myths, receives a score of 40 out of 100. The second component, settled and internalized results, receives a score of 20, the third component, the causal factors accelerating the existing institutionalization in the organization, receives a score of 20, and the fourth component, the institutional dimension of governance, receives a score of 20 out of 100. The framework mentioned above is used for scoring, as well as the inclusion of observations and personal judgment. The findings of calculating the institutionalization dimension and life cycle stage for SMEs are in Table 5.

Table 5. Measurement Results of Levels of Life-Cycle Stages and Degrees of Institutionalization

No.	Company	Stage	Age	Degree of Institutionalization out of 100
1	Labriz Hotel Tourism Trade LLC	1	5	5
2	EDS Injection Molding Inc.	3	25	30
3	Mutlu Metal Chemical Ind.Trade LLC	2	33	3
4	Element Paint Industry and Trade Inc.	2	15	13
5	Günak Const.Ind.Trade Inc	3	43	17
6	Cheya Hotels & Residences/ Phaselis	2	12	13
7	PDR Management Info. Consultancy Inc.	3	30	40
8	Deteks Chemical Industry Inc.	3	53	50
9	Tess Design Consult.Const.LLC	1	3	4
10	Körfezdeniz Const. Trade LLC	3	13	16
11	MTM Holography IT Inc	3	22	35
12	Oasis Tourism Ltd.	3	31	4
13	Adatepe Farm & Food Inc	1	21	4
14	b-fit Health Sports Investment Trade Inc.	3	13	22
15	Muzipo Kids Education Consultancy Inc.	2	8	11
16	Silk&Cashmere/ Fabeks Foreign Trade Inc.	3	28	61
17	e-data Technology LLC	2	19	6
18	Varer Machinery Ind.Trade LLC	2	13	6
19	Modern Packaging Ind.Trade Inc.	3	42	3
20	Saarpor Bosphorus Ind.Trade LLC	2	17	7

5. The second group of findings shows the relationships between life-cycle stages, age, and institutionalization variables, which are expressed with graphic representations.

Chart 1. Relationship between Age and Stage

5a. There is a relationship between age and stage, as can be expected.

5b. Chart 2 shows the relationship between the life cycle stage and institutionalization.

Chart 2. Life Cycle Stage and Institutionalisation Relationship

The institutional component and the life cycle phases are correlated linearly. The third stage firms Oasis and Modern are the two businesses that caused the anomaly in Chart 2. The scores of Modern and Oasis, which are included in this group but whose life cycle image assessments are passive and decreasing, seem to be quite low, even though the average of the third stage institutionalization dimension, omitting Modern and Oasis, is 33.9 points (3 and 4).

5c. The third graph looks at the institutional development status in relation to the age variable.

Chart 3. Age *and Institutionalization* *Relationship*

The development of the institutional component and the age variable are unrelated. According to organizational theory, the emergence of institutional aspects is more closely correlated with the evolution of the criteria that make up the life cycle

stage across time rather than age. The growth of institutionalization, on the other hand, may be argued to be more closely tied to the life cycle than to age from the perspective of IT.

5.d. Chart 4 represents the scenario after the two businesses that contribute to the irregularity in Chart 3 are removed.

Chart 4. Life Cycle Stages - Institutionalization Relationship (except for Oasis and Modern, which shows irregularity)

The life cycle idea is supported by the data. Theoretically, life phases rather than age are used to gauge an organization's or company's growth and development. The reasons why the two businesses produced abnormalities were investigated, and more interviews with the third-stage businesses Oasis and Modern led to the following findings.

Oasis and Modern are the two firms that seem to not be "active," even though they are both stage III enterprises. The thorough interview revealed that Modern made the decision to shut down at the conclusion of the first generation; it was found that Oasis is in a sluggish or unsure condition and is lacking "management vigor." While one of the partners in Oasis wishes to leave/sell the company and the other aims to integrate the second generation, this goal has not yet been realized, therefore it is left to the process. If "management energy" needs to be defined as a new term in this context, it may be said to be a kind of motivation as well as the entrepreneurial hunger of the managing partner or partners. While there are physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual elements to controlling energy, the first two are crucial. It could have anything to do with generation, age, feeling full, exhaustion, or another factor. Nonetheless, because we spend a third of our time working during those hours, it is important to consider this element. In general, it is low in older, more established, well managed generations; high in younger, just begun, or nonexistent generations. The governing generations will not be implicated in its annihilation or will disengage in due course. Effective managers of management energy move the company in the right direction.

5e. Once inconsistencies are removed from the remaining 18 firms, the first stage is made up of 3 companies (Tess, Labriz, and Adatepe), the second stage is made up of 7 companies (Cheya, Varer, Saarpur, e-data, Mutlu, Muzipo, and Element), and the third stage is made up of 8 companies (Gulf Denizli). are created, including, b fit, MTM, EDS, S&C, PDR, Günak, and Deteks. To calculate the institutionalization dimension score at each stage, the institutionalization dimensions of the firms in each group are averaged.

- Stage I average institutionalization dimension 4.3 points
- Stage II average institutionalization dimension 8.4 points

- Stage III average institutionalization dimension 33.8 points

According to the life-cycle model used here there is no fourth life cycle stage for small and medium-sized businesses. Alternatively, it is possible to indicate the anticipation of leaving SME status and moving to a bigger class. According to the study, businesses that have attained their IT legitimacy—that is, acquired a particular organizational size and structure—are those that are near to experiencing a class transition.

CONCLUSION

The growth of the open system natural organizational structures that make up the social structures of these businesses, as well as their ability to adapt to their institutional environments, are both important for the development and survival of SMEs. In terms of KT, the study's findings agree with the idea. The stage of the organization in its life cycle was established by the evaluation of 18 factors, each of which has a unique impact on the growth of businesses at each level. Like the institutional theory, it has been observed that organizations that have lagged in institutional development, have not adequately adapted to a location's environment, and for which some aspects of the social structure have not sufficiently developed as an institutional myth, are either unable to grow or are nearing the end of their life cycles. The study's novelty lay in the establishment of a special life cycle model for SMEs and of techniques for gauging organizational institutionalization.

The importance of corporate entrepreneurship and working factors in practice is demonstrated by the fact that the development of the corporate dimension in companies with corporate actors is higher than that of other companies, while SME partners or managers and the local academic environment have focused on the concept of institutionalization, removing ambiguities, Understanding the difference of organizational structure elements such as prof

Since managers or leaders of organizations are closely related to the dimension of institutionalization in terms of both organizational structure and communication with the external environment, corporate entrepreneurship studies can be thought of as suggestions for future research within the theory of organization. Academic research in this area will be devoted to expanding the application of KT in business science. What are the typical lifecycle traits that businesses exhibit that they may transmit to the next generations? What effect does population ecology theory have on the environment-organization connections life cycle model, which investigates the antithesis of institutional theory's similarity (isomorphism) approach (why are there

various organizations)? Are businesses only victims of their surroundings, or is institutional entrepreneurship a more significant factor?

Organizational theory continues to be significantly influenced by institutional theory. Yet, it has not been able to have a considerable influence on management research's ideas of organizational behavior. Therefore, it is incorrect to assume that managers do not have a significant impact on institutional theory. Throughout, I have attempted to sound an optimistic note. Institutional approach which is at an early stage of development, may be more visible, employable and measurable.

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ATTACHMENTS

APPENDIX 1. Company Basic Information Table

Company Full Name											
1	Year Founded/Company Type	Year:									
2	Field of Activity(s)										
3	Generation in Management (if Family Business)	Choose	I	I+II	II	II+III	III	III+			
3.1	Number of Family Members in Management/Company										
3.2	Family Council	Choose	—————→			there is		or	None		
3.3	Family Constitution	Choose	—————→			There is		or	None		
3.4	Succession Plan	Choose	—————→			there is		or	None		
4	Endorsement	Choose	1-3 M TL		3.1 – 25M			25.1-125			
4.1	Turnover Development	Million TL.	2019 budget	2018: 2017:	2015: 2015:	2014: 2013:	2012: 2011:	2010: 2009:	2008: 2007:	2006	
5	Investment	Million TL.	2019 budget								1980:
6	No of personnel										
6.1	White Collar/Blue Collar		/.....								
6.2	Women / Men		/.....								
6.3	Number of Regions/Facility, locations, and number of employees:										
7	Technology	Choose	Production	Trade/Retail	Service						
7.1	(If production) machine/human /semi-automatic	Choose	machine	Manual labor	Semi-automatic						
8	Corporate Departments	Choose	HR	Accounting	Cost Accounting	Planning	HSE	LAB	R&D		
9	Machinery – Equipment – Equipment List			Attach	Annex - I						
10	Organization chart			Attach	Annex II						
10.1	Previous org chart			Attach	Annex III						
10.2	(if any) Draft (future) org chart			Attach	Annex IV						
11	Total White Collar Formal Education + (if any) additional vocational education years:			Attach	Annex V						
12	Active membership to professional/social organizations			Attach	Annex VI						

APPENDIX 2. Institutional Dimension Analysis Questions and Scoring Template

INSTITUTIONAL DIMENSION ANALYSIS QUESTIONS:

1. Existence and adoption of rational myths (40 / 100)
 - 1.1. Professional programs (sales, accounting, cost control, ERP, CRM etc.)
 - 1.2. Technology (institutionalized, adopted, pervasive technologies)
 - 1.3. Data analysis / process (Data processing)
 - 1.4. HR: Formal recruitment policies
 - 1.5. OHS & Environmental programs and applications
 - 1.5.1. No smoking ban and other signs
 - 1.5.2. Smoking areas
 - 1.5.3. Waste recycling bins in offices
 - 1.6. Social and health insurance opportunities
 - 1.7. ISO and application practice / degree of adoption
 - 1.8. Formalization
 - 1.9. Professionalization
 - 1.10. Division of labor and specialization
 - 1.11. All kinds of certificates, accreditation, approvals
 - 1.12. An established and written reward system implementation
 - 1.13. Presence of management consultant, financial analyst, independent board member or other consulting firm if any
2. Institutional dimension monitoring by results (20/100)

2.1. Corporate culture

2.1.1. Corporate language, jargon

2.1.2. Established values

2.1.3. Shared beliefs and practices

2.1.4. Shared motion and action logic

2.2. Communication and communication channels and form

2.3. Organizational rigidity, resistance to change, structural
duality

2.4. Accepted, generalized business rules

2.5. Social activities, participations, projects, donations

3. Institutional dimension observation by cause factors (20/100)

3.1. Agents / agents : Leaders, professional organizations,
government, government agencies

3.1.1. Developing the learning capabilities of the
organization by providing the balance between stability and change because of a
leadership practice by institutional actors (leaders).

3.2.2. Management support (top and middle leaders)

3.2. Contractual relations

3.3. Normative organizations, successful and leading
organizations, professional organizations

3.4. International consulting (PWC, Deloitte, etc.)

4. Institutional dimension of governance (20/100)

4.1. In companies that do not have a family constitution, family council or family business, a detailed, incorporation charter beyond the legal framework

4.2. management transfer plan

4.3. Independent board member

4.4. International partnerships

4.5. Governance section staging template

- Family Council – 2 points
- Family Constitution – 2 points
- International partnerships – 2 points
- Future Management Plan (Succession Plan) – 2 points
- Matching personal and business goals – 2 points
- A strategy for business objectives – 2 points
- A business plan for the identified strategy – 2 points
- Sufficient resources for the plan – 1 point
- Independent board – 2 points
- Sufficient infrastructure for the plan – 1 point
- role (leader and management energy) for the plan – 2 points

APPENDIX 3. Life-Cycle Model for Small and Medium-Sized Firms

	FIRST STAGE	GROWTH & COLLECTIVITY STAGE	MATURITY & STRUCTURING STAGE (CASH-COW STAGE)	LOOK: Active / Passive / Decline
TURNOVER DEVELOPMENT & TURNOVER CHANGE	-	Rapid turnover increase	Turnover is close to horizontal	LOOK / APPEARANCE CRITERIA: Goal 1: Business goal / None / Personal goal orientation Strategy 2: Regeneration / None / Shrinkage - Shutdown 3. Organizational structure: Developed / Less structured 4. Investments (Machinery, equipment, real estate): Continued / Few / None 5. Management energy: Good / Less / No 6. Presence of a new leader and/or interest of the next generation 7. Corporate Governance: Yes / Intent / No
NUMBER OF STAFF / GENERATION IN MANAGEMENT	Little	Rapid growth, growing organization	Close to horizontal, there may be little increase	
PRODUCT / SERVICE	Single / Few	There is an increase. Product/service diversity. Investments possible	Slight increase	
MARKET	Narrow / Single	Expanding market. Investments	The goal is to protect the market	
SENIOR MANAGEMENT STYLE & FORM AND LEADERSHIP	Entrepreneur. Individual. One or two men	Directorate. Charismatic leadership can be seen. Quick and frequent decision making. Intervention from partners to day-to-day management	Delegation. Controlled delegation or observation	
ORGANIZATIONAL CHART, ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE and ORG. CHANGE	Informal (No formal structure)	Central	Moving away from the centre. Formation of functional structure	
COMMUNICATION AND RELATIONS	Informal (No formal structure)	(Systems) Formalization is starting, but communication is still informal	Formal. Written. Infrequent office meetings	
MANAGEMENT FOCUS, PURPOSE, AND OBJECTIVE	Produce-sell. Entrepreneurship activities. Exist. Emphasis on sourcing	Little concern for survival. Success. Grow. Production/product/service orientation. Efforts to establish a control mechanism. Goals are starting to emerge.	Internal coordination & problems. Predictable profitability. Emphasis on goals. Planning emphasis. Market growth. Efficiency focus. Decreased contact with the environment.	
CONTROL SYSTEM	Market results. Personal. Paternalistic.	Reporting. Cost calculations (cost control).System and simple planning initiatives.	Formal. Accounting system. Planning is important.	
REWARD SYSTEM	Subjective. Personal. Inherited from the father. By owners	Salary and rank increase. Contribution to success and personal bonuses.	Systematic (independent of the person). Profit distribution.	
LEVEL OF FORMALIZATION	No formalization	Usually, informal . There are some procedures .	Formal procedures . Departmentalization. Stable structure. Use of professional applications such as accepted planning/control/IT/HR programs	
PROFESSIONALIZATION / DIVISION OF LABOR	None	Staffing begins	Work sharing. Departmentalization	
INNOVATION	It is realized by the founder/partners. So many ideas, little planning	Maintained by employees and managers	Separate innovation/development groups	
CORPORATE DEPARTMENTS	-	Joint administrative staff. Division of labor around individuals rather than functions	HR-Accounting- Lab -OHS-Quality Control-Planning	
ORGANIZATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS (Behavior, Culture)	-	Unity, togetherness, dedication. Long working hours/time pressure	Conservatism. Rigidity. Increase in administrative activities	
RULES OF THE GAME	single target	Relationship/networking. Fame.	Regulation of increasing complexity. Brand.	
STRATEGY	None	Growth	There are strategic studies	
INVESTMENTS	Limited, core business focused	Fast investments	Close to horizontal, there may be little increase	
CRISIS				

APPENDIX 4. Qualitative Research Evaluation Chart

COMPANY

FOUNDATION / AGE (2019)

SIZE (TURNOVER / EMPLOYEE)

SCALE - I: DEGREE / LEVELS OF INSTITUTIONALIZATION

	Full Value	Formed value of the organisation
THE EXISTENCE OF RATIONAL MYTHS	40	
INSTALLED AND INSIDERED RESULTS	20	
WHY FACTORS	20	
GOVERNANCE – Institutional dimension	20	

SCALE – II:LIFE-CYCLE PHASE (One of the three stages and appearance value)

I	II	III	APPEARANCE
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NOTES: